

A NEW STAGE OF PERFORMANCE ART IN SCENE SPEECH AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the relationship between artificial intelligence (AI) and stage speech as the intersection of modern theater art and digital technologies. The study examines speech synthesis, voice models (Voice Cloning), diction and intonation transformation in acting, and the aesthetic functions of stage language in the era of "techno-humanism". The possibilities of restoring historical voices (Digital Resurrection) using digital avatars and neural networks and their impact on the quality of stage performance are scientifically substantiated.

Today, artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming an active participant in the process of artistic creation. Theatrical art, in particular, one of its most important elements - stage speech - was not left out of this technological wave. In the first quarter of the 21st century, digital technologies have rapidly penetrated all spheres of human life, including the culture and art system.

Stage speech is the foundation of acting mastery and the primary means of conveying the symbolic and semantic meanings of the word hour to the audience. K.S. Stanislavsky, the founder of the psychological school of theater, said: "The word on stage is an action." [1]. In modern theatrical art, this "movement" is enriched with the capabilities of neural networks, voice algorithms, and digital acoustics. The impact of artificial intelligence on stage speech is twofold: on the one hand, it opens up new opportunities for performing arts, and on the other hand, it poses a threat of falsifying the power of the voice, its naturalness, and human emotions. Therefore, it became clear that when using it, industry specialists approach actors and directors with caution.

The issue of the synthesis of artificial intelligence and art has been a subject of extensive debate within the global scientific community in recent years. In particular, S. Dixon, who conducted research in the field of digital theater and media art, emphasizes in his works that digital technologies do not disrupt the traditional system of theater, but rather expand its performative capabilities. [2]. Research by scientists at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) is of great importance in the field of speech synthesis and artificial learning of voice intonation algorithms. In particular, A. Waksman studied the ability of neural networks to detect and imitate hidden emotions in the human voice. [3]. The theory of stage speech and the influence of modern technical means on it have formed as a separate direction in Russian and Uzbek theater studies. V.N. Galendeev, a professor at the St. Petersburg

Institute of Performing Arts, conducted a psychological analysis of "The propagation of an actor's speech in the acoustic space and the influence of sound amplifiers on it." [4].

Although the problems of stage speech and diction in the art of speech in Uzbekistan, the skill of working with words have been studied in the scientific works of M. Alamova and Kh. Ikramova. [5], the impact of artificial intelligence on stage language and analysis within the framework of the "techno-humanism" concept have not yet been sufficiently systematized. The research process utilized methods of systematicity, comparative-historical analysis, model classification, and expert evaluation. Artificial intelligence has been applied to stage speech. Real-time filtering of sound quality using neural networks and adaptation to stage acoustics gave rise to acoustic-technological directions. The creative-performing direction allowed for the creation of voice models and the digital reconstruction of historical voices. Control over the process of working with diction and voice in acting education through AI simulators. Speech synthesis and digital voice modeling have developed a pedagogical direction.

Currently, artificial intelligence programs such as -ElevenLabs and -VALL-E- (Microsoft) are capable of creating a full speech model using a 3-second sample of a person's voice. In the performing arts, this technology opens the doors to "digital reincarnation." For example, it is possible to create new stage works or audio plays based on the sound recordings of great actors and speakers who have passed away. From a scientific perspective, the mathematical model of voice accounts for the formant frequencies, timbre, tempo-rhythm, and pauses of human speech. A neural network (e.g., *Wavenet*) generates a speech wave (W) based on the following mathematical algorithm: Here, each subsequent speech element (w_t) is synthesized by the system with human spontaneity, depending on the chain of sounds preceding it. However, stage speech is not a simple means of transmitting information. It contains an internal subtext and a psychological task. Artificial intelligence can read text, but it does not yet perceive the "scenic intent" as humans do.

In theatrical halls, the transmission of sound to the audience and the accuracy of diction are the most critical criteria. During our research, the amplitude-frequency indicators of the actor's voices were analyzed using AI algorithms. AI-driven sound processing automatically adjusts the sound coming from the actor's microphone on stage based on the acoustic situation in the hall. When the sound waves of stage speech are filtered using neural networks, it becomes possible to convey a whispered word clearly to the very last row of the hall without overloading the actor's voice. This allows the director to work on new psychological mise-en-scene.

Mobile and computer programs based on AI can monitor a student's independent work on diction when teaching stage speech disciplines in art higher education institutions. The neural network listens to the student's quick phrases, poetic texts, or monologues, and performs the following:

- Omission of consonant sounds (assimilation and dissimilation errors);
- Incorrect placement of logical pauses in the text;
- Real-time detection of errors such as volume decrease or excessive volume increase (dynamic range distortion). This process allows the student to work on themselves individually and bring their speech to a flawless level even outside of pedagogical control.

The results obtained show that artificial intelligence has an unprecedented effect on improving the technical and acoustic aspects of stage speech. However, the aesthetic and philosophical aspects of the issue remain controversial. As H.-T. Lehmann (Hans-Thies Lehmann), a representative of the German school of theater studies, emphasized in his concept of "post-dramatic theater," the main power of theater is living communication that occurs "here and now." [6]. If a voice played by a digital avatar or fully synthesized by artificial intelligence plays on stage, the theater loses its primary feature—the live energy exchange. There are also legal and ethical issues with the use of voice models. The reproduction of a deceased actor's voice on stage without their consent requires serious discussions within the framework of legislation and creative ethics.

In our opinion, artificial intelligence should not replace the actor in stage speech, but should act as a virtual "partner" that enriches his voice and strengthens the idea of directing. We can call this phenomenon the "theater of the era of techno-humanism." As a result of scientific research and analysis, artificial intelligence is a new possibility for stage speech. It provides high artistic efficiency in the creation of sound synthesis and digital voice models in the theater, the reproduction of the voices of historical figures and multimedia performances. No perfect neural network can completely replace the internal psychological subtext of stage speech, the inner experiences of the actor, and the live energetic connection with the audience. Therefore, AI serves as an auxiliary tool in the art of stage speech. In the art of the performer's stage speech, the person remains the most important factor. In conclusion, the synthesis of artificial intelligence and stage speech in the theater of the future will not destroy the traditional theater school, but will adapt it to the requirements of the digital age and contribute to the development of new performative forms.

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